

Journey to Darkness

Laying flat on my back,
staring at the sky,
fixing my gaze on a bright star—
is the star looking at me,
or am I looking at the star?

It doesn't matter.

The fear of being lost is gone.
Realization of truth
has demolished the ghost of fear.

Vastness can be mapped,
depth can be gauged,
even
darkness can be realized.

But
obstacles cannot deter
a true seeker—
They exist
to be conquered.

Truth has shown its presence
in the flicker of lightning.
Thunder has deafened the silence.

The knowledge of rain has arrived,
quenching the thirst.

A faint light far away from the star
is like a key of hope—
enough to catch off guard
even the vanguard.

Aditya Mishra